

EDEN ISS

D7.8 - Plant Growth Experiment Tray Toolkit

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WP 7 - Dissemination and Exploitation

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Executive summary

This document describes the activities around the experiment tray toolkit as an exclusive education tool for school children and pupils. The tool kits have been developed by DLR and highlight the key issues of Controlled Environment Agriculture (CEA) technologies and different growth procedures related to cultivating plants in space. Here, the pupils can learn different aspects about Bio-regenerative Life Support Systems (BLSS) and the role of higher plants in human space exploration endeavors.

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1 EDEN for Kids Outreach Program incl. Experimental Tool Kit

1.1 Educational Program

Already in 2015 the EDEN ISS DLR project team started the development of the educational program called *EDEN for Kids*, which is carried out in close collaboration with the DLR_School_Lab to encourage pupils in Germany (and Europe) to learn about the key issues of Controlled Environment Agriculture (CEA) technologies and different growth procedures related to cultivating plants in space. Besides the lecture material for school classes (in English), dedicated plant growing tray tool kits were developed.

Figure 1: left: EDEN for Kids Logo; Right: DLR School_Lab logo

1.2 Tray Tool Kit Equipment Overview

Each school class gets three different plant growing boxes equipped with an adjustable LED illumination system to test plant growth with various light set ups.

Figure 2 – Setup of the experiment tool kit with three different light intensities

The tool kit is equipped with small clay pots, cress seeds, a temperature and humidity sensor, a water sprayer (for irrigation purposes) and two different soils to simulate Earth and Mars substrate. An additionally a user manual was worked out with students and is supplied to set up the growth boxes

correctly. The LED light spectrum can be chosen between green, blue, red and white. With this tool kit multiple research questions can be examined.

Figure 3 – Overview of the experiment tool kit materials

Figure 4 – Two tool kits incl. worked out user manual.

Figure 5 – Grow results under pure green light regime

1.3 Content of Teaching

The educational tool kits were developed within the EDEN ISS group, the team of the DLR Bremen School_lab and two master works of the University of Bremen, Germany (see Reference List). In principle the connected educational program is divided into three research phases. In the beginning (phase 1) the school kids are getting an introduction into plant growing and cultivation and discuss the different aspects of growing plants on Earth and Mars. In small groups the pupils work out possible problems of growing plants on Mars and present it to each other. Optional the EDEN ISS team presented the latest status of the EDEN ISS project and the reason for this research.

Figure 6 – Introduction workshop inside the educational lab of the DLR School_Lab in Bremen (Germany)

After this introduction phase, the plant tool kits are handed out (phase 2) to the school class to take it back into their class rooms to start plant growing experiments with cress. Among others, the research question is what the optimal light colour for plant growing is. Also the different simulates were part of different experiments.

After conduction of the experiments, the school class comes back to the DLR_School_Lab presenting the results of the plant growing experiments (phase 3).

Figure 7: Pupil during final result presentation inside the DLR school lab. The pupils had to visualize their own results.

During phase three the school classes received additional information about controlled environment agriculture technologies (via dedicate presentations) or through EDEN laboratory visits as well as visits of the EDEN ISS MTF (only during AIT). Please see pictures of the impression chapter.

1.4 Performance of the project and outlook

Both groups - teachers and pupils - were highly motivated and gave a positive feedback to this outreach- and educational programme. In particular, the combination between aerospace and horticulture seemed to catch the attention. Pupils as well as teachers were excited about the project because of a close cooperation between researchers of DLR and school teachers who constantly improve the program. The program is running in its fourth year so far and has engaged between 3 to 5 school classes per year, which sums up into ca. 18 - 20 classes in total since the start in 2015.

The age group varied between grade 6 to 11, however mostly classes of grade 7 were involved because of the introduction of the topic of plant growth is introduced at that age. Some of the schools ran the project for more than one year with different classes.

The tool kit designs and the accompanying outreach program are in a constant improvement phase. The following development steps are envisioned for the experimental tool kit in the future, after the official project has ended:

- The experiment phase will be extended in collaboration with the educational institution in Bremen called Botanika (<https://www.botanika-bremen.de>) to experience a bigger scale greenhouse and its implemented greenhouse techniques. Accompanied by different presentations the school kids will deal with questions of sustainability and future horticultural technologies such as vertical farming.
- Professional and bigger scale plant growing box will be implemented, which will permanently be installed in schools to run plant growing experiments continuously. These tool kits are presently under development (with the company Agrilution: <https://agrilution.de/>).
- The tool kits, the user manual, and the teacher's manual will be translated into English and Italian for a broader coverage within Europe and the main consortium partner states.
- A teaching video will be developed as an additional educational communication tool.

1.5 Impressions

In the following section some impressions of the accompanying activities are displayed.

Figure 8 – Pupils during the visit of the EDEN lab , investigating the grow results of the self-build bottle crop tool kits (lecture material)

Figure 9 – Pupils during the visit of the EDEN lab with Dr. Schubert, investigating the grow results of the self-build bottle crop tool kits (lecture material)

Figure 10 – Pupil’s group picture in front of the MTF after final presentation day

Figure 11 – Dedicated MTF tour for the school class after final presentation of the tool kit experiments

References

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